

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF SQUEEZE CASTED CONTINUOUS SiC/Al COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Continuous SiC fiber reinforced metal matrix composite(MMC)s are manufactured with using the optimal processing condition of single fiber reinforced MMCs in a vacuum assisted squeeze casting system. The stress-strain behaviors of these squeeze casted MMC specimens are observed at different temperatures between -50 °C and 350 °C for their high temperature strength retention. The effect of isothermal exposure on the mechanical properties of these MMC specimens is also investigated.

INTRODUCTION

Squeeze casting among the impregnation methods of metal matrix composite (MMC)s has been considered a quite promising method particularly for the fabrication of continuous fiber reinforced aluminum matrix composites[1-2]. Consisting of several remedial steps such as applied pressure and preheating of fibers for poor wettability between reinforcing ceramic fibers and liquid metal matrix brings in general defect-free, fine grains, and relatively good interfacial bonding MMCs by this squeeze casting. However, this several steps of the process is very sensitively depend on the optimal manufacturing process for obtaining sound MMCs[3-4].

In this study, continuous SiC fiber reinforced aluminum matrix composites are manufactured with using the results of the previous work[5]. Therefore, the aim of this study is to prove the applicability of the optimal processing condition obtained with using single continuous fiber reinforced MMCs for actual bundled fiber reinforced MMCs through the observation of their mechanical properties. In order to do this purpose, these squeeze casted SiC/Al MMCs are measured their tensile strength at room temperature as well as high temperature up to 350 °C. The tensile test of these MMCs at the sub-zero temperature of -50 °C is also performed. From this observation, it is believed that the stress-strain behaviors at different temperatures can give some clues to define the beginning of the stage II-plastic deformation of the matrix- as well as the limit of the strength retention at high temperature. The effect of isothermal exposure is also investigated for these squeeze casted MMCs to give the reference data for the tempering. Finally, how different composition of the matrix alloy affects on the tensile strength and the interface of MMC are observed with using X-ray diffraction and SEM for pure Al and Al-13%Si alloy matrix.

FABRICATION OF CONTINUOUS SiC/Al MMC

Continuous SiC fiber reinforced MMC specimens are fabricated in a vacuum assisted squeeze casting system. Reinforcing SiC fiber is Nicalon SiC fiber and the matrix are two kinds of pure Al and Al-13%Si alloy. The fabrication sequence is represented in Fig.1. The manufacturing process here is referred to the optimal manufacturing process range of single continuous Boron fiber reinforced MMCs[5] except the applied pressure. The pressure drop during the impregnation of melting matrix into the fibers is so higher in smaller diameter of fibers that the applied pressure is 70MPa for SiC/Al MMC compared with 40 MPa for B/Al MMC. The other conditions relative to the temperature in Ref.5 are directly applied for manufacturing SiC/Al MMC.

INTERFACES OF SiC/Al MMC

Although Nicalon SiC fiber used here is not pure, it is well compatible with the matrix of Al during the squeeze casting process. As shown in Fig.2, the interfaces of squeeze casted SiC/Al MMCs show no chemically reacted layer with both matrices of pure Al and Al-13%Si in optical microscopic observation. The reason of no reaction zone in the interfaces can be explained that the liquid metal contacts the SiC fiber very short time in this squeeze casting process. Thus, the fiber degradation is not possibly occurred if the process condition is well prepared in the squeeze casting. However, the matrix of Al-13%Si makes eutectic Si around the interfaces as shown in Fig.3. X-ray diffraction as shown in Fig.4 confirmed this eutectic Si in SiC/Al-13% MMCs. Thus, Al-13%Si which originally taken for its good fluidity causes such eutectic Si as to reduce the tensile strength of fabricated composites adversely.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AT HIGH TEMPERATURE

Squeeze casted SiC/Al MMC specimens are measured their tensile strength at different temperatures to prove their excellent strength retention at high temperature. Fig.5 shows the variation of their tensile strength with respect to the temperature between -50 °C and 350 °C. From this figure, the tensile strength at room temperature is very close to the theoretical value on the basis of the rule of mixture. Furthermore, this value is kept up to 350 °C with insignificant change. Fig.6 shows their stress-strain behaviors at three different temperatures. It is found in this figure that the transition point from the matrix elastic region to the matrix plastic region stage II is a little bit lower than the matrix yielding strength at room temperature. On the other hand, the transition points of the stress-strain curve at low(-50 °C) and high(150 °C) temperatures are higher than the point at room temperature. For this increased elastic range at 150 °C, it is explained with the assumption of the perfect bonding that the thermally induced residual stresses in the matrix are released and redistributed to the constituent materials because higher thermal expansion coefficient of the matrix expands more than the fiber to be compressed at high temperature. For the case of -50 °C, the same idea as the above causes the result contrary to the observed effect. However, this phenomena is agreed with the result according to the prestrain theory[6]. Finally, Fig.7 shows the effect of isothermal exposure on the tensile strength of squeeze casted SiC/Al MMCs. The tensile strength of these MMCs changes insignificantly for the isothermal exposure at 300 °C for 24 hours. However, at 500 °C for 24 hours, the tensile strength is dropped suddenly to be less than 90% compared

with the value at room temperature. It is supposed for this reason that the interfacial bonding is weakened or broken at 500 °C exposure because this temperature causes chemically reacted layer at the interfaces. This consideration is confirmed by finding the reaction layer in SEM observation.

CONCLUSIONS

Mechanical properties including the stress-strain behaviors of squeeze casted SiC/Al MMCs at different temperatures are investigated to know their excellent high temperature performance. According to the obtained results, the following conclusions could be derived;

- (1) Squeeze casted SiC/Al MMC retains the longitudinal tensile strength at room temperature up to 350 °C.
- (2) The elastic range of this MMC is increased a little more at either -50 °C or 150 °C than the range at room temperature.
- (3) The effect of the isothermal exposure for 24 hours is not significant up to 300 °C but at 500 °C such as 12% reduction of the tensile strength

Thus, optimal processing condition referred to single fiber reinforced MMCs can be well applied to make actual bundled fiber reinforced MMCs which have excellent high temperature performances.

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Fig.1 The Fabrication Sequence of SiC/Al MMC in a Vacuum Assisted Squeeze Casting

(a)

(b)

Fig.2 Microstructures of Squeeze Casted MMC (a)SiC/Al-13%Si (b)SiC/Al (x400)

Fig.3 SEM Microstructure of SiC/Al-13%Si(x3200)

Fig.4 X-ray Diffraction Patterns of SiC/Al (a)SiC/Al-13%Si, as-cast (b)SiC/Al,as-cast (c)SiC/Al, 500 °C for 24Hrs.

Fig.5 Tensile Strength Versus Temperatures for SiC/Al

Fig.6 Stress-Strain Curve of SiC/Al at Different Temperatures

Fig.7 Effect of Isothermal Exposure on the Tensile Strength of SiC/Al